

P07**IsletNet, built-in validation tools, a multi-center validation study proposal**

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Background

IsletNet, a web-based service, was developed as a digital alternative [1] to the traditional manual islet quantification approach [2]. It has been trained using islet images from interested centers [3]. We aim to propose now a multi-center validation study of IsletNet. To this end we introduce the integrated validation tools (Fig. 1A).

Methods

Simple Comparison tool is designed to compare IsletNet to a local trusted method (Fig. 1B). Pixel-to-Pixel Comparison tool facilitates a detailed comparison with annotated images. Isolated islets were counted manually; the counts were entered into an xlsx file from IsletNet. Simultaneously, images were acquired, and manual annotations were created. The manual counts, original images, and annotations were uploaded to the respective validation tools. IsletNet generated graphs (pdf) and tables (xlsx) which were downloaded for analysis.

Results

The manual islet counts (x-axis, Fig. 2A) with those automatically determined by IsletNet (y-axis, Fig. 2A). It also compares the manually estimated islet volumes (x-axis, Fig. 2B, Ricordi table selected in Fig 1B) with the automatic measurements by IsletNet (y-axis, Fig. 2B). The Pixel-to-Pixel Comparison tool depicts the islet contours and the separation lines (Fig. 2D) , compares the automated segmentation of the original images with the expert annotations (Fig. 2C,E), and it produces histograms that juxtapose the automated analysis with the manual ground truth (Fig. 2F). This tool also generates tables showing various metrics like sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, and F1 score, alongside relative errors in islet counts and volumes using different islet shape models.

Conclusions

The integrated validation tools are prepared for an independent multi-center validation study of IsletNet. A detailed proposal for this study is forthcoming, and participation from all centers is encouraged.

Fig. 1: The validation tools in IsletNet (screenshots).

Fig. 2: The automatic output of the validation tools.

Conflicts of interest

No conflicts declared

References

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[3] Islet Centers contributing images for IsletNet training: Uppsala, A. Friberg; Oslo, H. Scholz; Lille, V. Gmyr, J. Kerr-Conte; Geneva, D. Bosco; Leiden, J. Doppenberg; Minneapolis, J. Wilhelm; Chicago, P. Witkowski; Newcastle upon Tyne, M. Honkanen-Scott; City of Hope, H. Komatsu; Oxford, R. Spiers.